

The Coupling Constants Series and the Perfect Symmetry of Hadrons

O Manor

June 11, 2021

Abstract:

In this paper, the author will analyze the hadronic structure as manifested in the coupling constant series, within the framework of the new 8-theory. Analysis will be made according to the first representation of the coupling constant series, net variations. The numerical first term from the left in each coupling term indicate a perfect hadronic structure, which have outstanding symmetry. The symmetry than is breaking due to an additional element coming from outside the hadron, the Majestic (3).

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.11)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

Notice that from the second coupling term and above, the hadron is presented as $(8 * 3) = 24$ multiples. $(8 * 3)$ is not just a regular number, in number theory it has quite an incredible features. The leech lattice, which has most density within a certain dimensional range, is intimately related to this number. In the 8-Theory however there is no use of any lattices. Rather we use variations. Notice the 24 is perfectly to and three divisible to vanish into matter. There is no additional variation left alone. The hadron is perfectly compact and most dense because of that trait. Than it is destabilized by additional term, the element in which we called the majestic (3). The point one was trying to make is that the perfect symmetry of the hadronic structure is preserved along each coupling term, i.e. each interaction. In addition, it is than lessen by the electron, i.e. the additional element in the third coupling term. And either the electron is also the cause of that symmetry break in all other terms or electron analogues field.

$$\frac{24 * N_V}{\text{mod}(6)} = 0; \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V = 2V + 1; V \geq 1$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P}$$

If it was any other number than 24, than the symmetry of the hadrons was not perfect, as equation (1.2) will not hold. The symmetry is breaking due to an external element added by the higgs field from the second element and above, the majestic (3). It is currently unclear whether this element is the same for each of the coupling terms. For the electric, it was proven the electron. However, for the weak interaction term and higher terms it could be an electron analogues particle manifested in the element (3) as mentioned in the previous paragraph and again, it's so important one wanted to emphasize it here as well. There are two main points to take from this short essay. The first is the perfect symmetry of the hadronic structure due to its numerical features. The second point is that the symmetry is breaking from an external element not from within the hadronic structure, due to the higgs field, inserting the majestic (3).

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)